

**ANALYSIS OF TIME MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES FOR
INSTRUCTION IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN
ELGEYO MARAKWET COUNTY, KENYA**

Kapkiai Charles Kipkoech

M.Ed Candidate

Moi University, Kenya

Declaration by the Candidate

This thesis is my original work and has never been presented for a degree or a diploma course in any other university or institution of higher learning.

.....
Kapkiai Charles Kipkoech

Date: August 8th 2017

Dedication

I dedicate this work to my dear parents, dad Jacob Kapkiai and mum Helena Kipsat who sacrificed their limited resources during my formative years in school. God bless them.

Abstract:

The study analyzed teacher spending of instructional time in public secondary schools. Objectives were to examine; teacher preparation, teaching interruptions and teachers' commitment. Pickle Jar Theory was applied. Research design was descriptive survey, while stratified random sampling was used to select 23 schools from 75. Questionnaires, interview schedule and document analysis were used. Validity was checked by expert review, test re-test technique was done for reliability. Results were presented using; frequency, percentages, tables and statements. Major finding was teaching interruptions reduce teaching time. Main recommendation was teachers shouldn't allow unplanned activities. Findings and recommendations will be useful to teachers.

Keywords: hidden causes, incompleteness of syllabus, teaching time, teaching interruptions

List of Figures

Figure 1: Diagram of Conceptual Framework

465

List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

AGM	:	Annual General Meeting
CIEM	:	Curriculum Instruction and Educational Media
DOS	:	Director of Studies
EFA	:	Education for All
EMC	:	Elgeyo Marakwet County
ERSWC	:	Economic Recovery Strategy for Wealth and Employment Creation
G/C	:	Guidance and Counseling
GoK	:	Government of Kenya
HOD	:	Head of Department
HOS	:	Head of Subject
KESSP	:	Kenya Education Sector Support Program
KESSHA	:	Kenya Secondary Schools Heads Association
KCSE	:	Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education
KICD	:	Kenya Institute of Curriculum Development
KNEC	:	Kenya National Examination Council
MDGS	:	Millennium Development Goals
MOE	:	Ministry of Education

N/A	:	Not Applicable
NEA	:	National Education Association
Phd	:	Doctor of Philosophy
PRSC	:	Poverty Reduction Strategy Paper
QASO	:	Quality Assurance and Standard Officer
SMASSE	:	Strengthening of Mathematics and Science in Secondary Education
SPSS	:	Software Program for Social Sciences
UNICEF	:	United Nations International Children Education Fund
USA	:	United States of America
8.4.4	:	Current system of education in Kenya; referring to 8 years for Primary education, 4 years Secondary education and another 4 years for University Education.

TABLE OF CONTENT

DECLARATION BY THE CANDIDATE	456
ABSTRACT:.....	Error! Bookmark not defined.
DEDICATION.....	456
LIST OF FIGURES	457
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS	457
TABLE OF CONTENT	459
LIST OF TABLES	460
ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	460
CHAPTER ONE.....	461
INTRODUCTION TO THE STUDY	461
1.1 Background of Study.....	461
1.2 Statement of the Problem	462
1.3 The Purpose of the Study	462
1.4 Significance of the study	462
1.5 Scope and Limitations of the Study	463
1.6 Assumptions of the Study	463
1.7 Objectives of the Study	463
1.8 Research Questions	464
1.9 Conceptual Framework	464
1.10 Theoretical Framework.....	465
CHAPTER TWO.....	467
LITERATURE REVIEW	467
2.1 Introduction.....	467
2.2 Teacher Preparation in Teaching.....	467
2.3 Teaching Time Interruptions	468
2.4 Teacher Commitment to Instruction.....	469
2.4.1 Teacher Absenteeism	470
CHAPTER THREE	472
RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY	472
3.1 Introduction.....	472
3.2 Study Area.....	472
3.3 Research Design.....	472
3.4 Target Population	472
3.5 Sampling Procedures and Sample Size	472
3.6 Data Collection Instruments	475
3.6.1 Questionnaire.....	475
3.6.2 Interview Schedules	475
3.6.3 Document Analysis.....	475
3.7 Piloting of Research Instruments.....	475
3.7.1 Validity	476
3.7.2 Reliability.....	476
3.8 Data Collection Procedures.....	476
3.9 Data Analysis	476

3.9.1 Ethical Considerations	476
CHAPTER FOUR	478
DATA ANALYSIS, PRESENTATION, INTERPRETATION AND DISCUSSIONS.....	478
4.1 Introduction.....	478
4.2 Teacher Preparation Towards Time Management Strategies in Public Secondary Schools	478
4.2.1 Preparation for Teaching as a Strategy in Management of Teaching Time	478
4.2.2 Content Presentation Strategies in Teaching Time Management	479
4.3 Teaching Interruptions and Time Management in Public Secondary Schools	480
4.3.1 Teaching Time Interruptions	480
4.3.2 Effect of Teaching Interruption on Syllabus Coverage	484
4.4 Teacher’s Commitment on Instruction as a Strategy for Management of Teaching Time	484
CHAPTER FIVE	489
SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS	489
5.1 Introduction.....	489
5.2 Summary of the Findings	489
5.2.1 Lesson preparation towards time management strategies in public secondary schools in Elgeyo Marakwet County	489
5.2.2 Teaching time interruptions in public secondary schools in Elgeyo Marakwet County	489
5.2.3 Teacher commitment towards time management strategies for instruction in public secondary schools in Elgeyo Marakwet County	489
5.3 Conclusions	490
5.4 Recommendations	490
REFERENCES	490
APPENDIX I: QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEACHERS	494
APPENDIX II: INTERVIEW GUIDE WITH THE DIRECTOR OF STUDIES	498

LIST OF TABLES

Table 3. 1: Sample Size	474
Table 4. 1: Teacher Preparation and Use of Schemes of Work as a Strategy of Time Management	479
Table 4. 2: Content Presentation in Teaching Time Management	480
Table 4. 3: Teaching Interruptions Experienced by Teachers	481
Table 4. 4: Nature of Teaching Interruptions and Time Management Strategies	482
Table 4. 5: Teachers’ Authority over Teaching Interruptions and Effect on Syllabus Coverage	483
Table 4. 6: Teacher’s Commitment on Instruction as a Strategy of Teaching Time Management	485
Table 4. 7: Teacher’s Creativity in Teaching as a Strategy of Time Management	487

Acknowledgement

I acknowledge the following persons who assisted me in the process of developing this research thesis. Much thanks goes to my research supervisors, Dr. Violet Nabwire Kafwa and Prof. Jackson Too. Their valuable time and effort put on this study is here acknowledged.

My heartfelt gratitude also goes to my dear wife Loice, our lovely daughters; Stephanie, Carol and Marion for their support and encouragement.

Lastly, and above all, I acknowledge the Almighty God’s will.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION TO THE STUDY

1.1 Background of Study

For many years now, the Kenyan secondary school syllabi content has been perceived to be wide by teachers. For this reason, since inception, the 8.4.4 secondary syllabus has been reviewed twice to address this challenge. The first review was done in 1992 followed by another in 2002. The main reasons for these reviews were to make curriculum more relevant, adequate and address issues of coverage.

Since then, still many teachers have not been able to complete syllabus on time with learners as expected. A study conducted by Mwangi (2011) on syllabus coverage in public secondary schools, revealed that syllabus was not covered before the end of the year for a particular class. When syllabus is completed in time, students have humble time for revision and good preparation for final examinations. Which results in good performance. This explains why, teachers and students get pressure from school administration, government and parents to end syllabus on time, Nyagundi (2012).

Syllabus completion on time has been used as a solution to address the issue of academic performance at secondary level. The Kenyan secondary school performance has not been good. The KNEC report (2010), show that a massive 154,830 students representing 43% of the total candidature obtained D+, D, D- and E in KCSE examinations. The KNEC report (2008) also reveal that only 25% of students scored at least a mean grade of C+ in KCSE, with girls being less likely than boys to score at least a C+ (a minimum grade required for university admission). The performance was worse in district schools, where only 11% of students scored at least a C+, compared to 43% in provincial schools and 90% in national schools.

Another problem facing syllabus completion is teacher absenteeism. According to Ongeri & Bii (2012), teacher absenteeism is a persistent problem in many countries as it reduces the quality of education and results in poor performance of students. Teachers lose teaching time.

Studies also has shown that teachers engage learners in activities that are not core to teaching and learning. For instance, in England, according to Merriam (2009) teachers were concerned with tasks that take sizable chunk of their time which has no value to teaching and learning process. For example, engaging learners in games, speeches, farm activities and cleanliness during class hours. Many at times teachers attend meetings and seminars during teaching hours of school.

In order to complete syllabus on time, teachers resort to teach syllabus during irregular school hours such as early morning, evening, weekends and holidays, Drucker (2005) and Ngugi (2013). Without them doing so, syllabus for a class spill over to the next. However, syllabus for a class has been structured and organized to be completed within a school term and academic year as well. This is a challenge many teachers in secondary schools in Kenya face.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

A study conducted by Mwangi (2011) on syllabus coverage in public secondary schools, revealed that syllabus was not covered before the end of the year. When syllabus is completed in time, students have humble time for revision and good preparation for final examinations. Which results in good performance. This explains why, teachers and students get pressure from school administration, government and parents to end syllabus on time, Nyagundi (2012), Sub-County Director of Education, Keiyo. One of the factors for incompleteness of syllabus on time is teacher absenteeism, Ongeru & Bii (2012), however there are other factors which this study sought to establish.

In order to complete syllabus on time, teachers resort to teaching extra hours away from the stipulated regular hours of school. Without them doing so, syllabus for a class spill over to the next. However, curriculum has been structured and organized to end within a school term and academic year as well. This is a dilemma teachers in many secondary schools in Kenya, find themselves in.

This situation reveals gaps in management of teaching time in many secondary schools which this study was intended to address. Time related issues in teaching such as holiday teaching, Gichunga (2011), uncovered syllabus, Mwangi (2011), teaching on weekends, Sulo (2012), teacher absenteeism, Ongeru & Bii (2012), and cheating in exams (KNEC Report, 2011) are indicators of improper time use in teaching in secondary schools. Therefore, this study was carried out to analyze hidden causes of incompleteness of syllabus in public secondary schools in Elgeyo Marakwet County.

1.3 The Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this thesis was to analyze time management strategies for instruction in public secondary schools in Elgeyo Marakwet County.

1.4 Significance of the study

This research will help identify existing gaps in the management of teaching time in public secondary schools in EMC. It will also be of importance to teachers in

overcoming time-related challenges in schools. The government education officers will find it useful.

1.5 Scope and Limitations of the Study

(i) Scope

The study was both quantitative and qualitative in approach. The study applied the Pickle Jar Theory of time management advanced by Jeremy Wright.

The study research design was descriptive survey. The instruments for data collection were the questionnaires, interview schedule and document analysis.

The statistical analyses were frequencies and percentages on tables as well as statement descriptions.

The study findings were generalized from analysis of a sample applied to the whole population of Elgeyo Marakwet County. The data collection instruments for the study were self-developed by the researcher.

(ii) Limitations

The study was limited by time factor.

The researcher faced financial constraints in facilitating the study and therefore had to use a sample population to overcome the time and financial constraints.

1.6 Assumptions of the Study

- (i) That there are time management strategies on instruction in public secondary schools in Elgeyo Marakwet County.
- (ii) That teachers prepare lessons before teaching in public secondary schools in Elgeyo Marakwet County.
- (iii) That teachers have strategies on managing interruptions in teaching in public secondary schools in Elgeyo Marakwet County.
- (iv) That teachers have some commitment towards time management strategies in public secondary schools in Elgeyo Marakwet County.

1.7 Objectives of the Study

The study focused on three objectives namely;

- (i) To examine teacher lesson preparation towards time management strategies in public secondary schools in Elgeyo Marakwet County.
- (ii) To establish teacher management strategies on interruptions during teaching time in public secondary schools in Elgeyo Marakwet County.
- (iii) To assess teacher commitment towards time management strategies for instruction in public secondary schools in Elgeyo Marakwet County.

1.8 Research Questions

- (i) What are the time management strategies on teacher lesson preparation in public secondary schools in EMC?
- (ii) What are the teacher management strategies towards interruptions during teaching time in public secondary schools in EMC?
- (iii) What is the teacher commitment level towards time management strategies in public secondary schools in EMC?

1.9 Conceptual Framework

The framework shows the relationship between time management strategies and instruction with respect to academic achievement in public secondary schools in EMC. Teaching time management (Independent Variable) determines the success of instruction (Dependent Variable), depending on how it is done by teachers. If teaching time management is done properly, good instruction of learners is realized. Consequently, good academic achievement is obtained. The converse is also true. Academic achievement of learners was used to measure instruction.

By implication, the same variable was also used to measure teaching time management by teachers.

Figure 1: Diagram of Conceptual Framework

Source: Researcher (2015)

1.10 Theoretical Framework

The study was guided by the Pickle Jar theory of time management advanced by Wright (2002). The theory is based on the idea that teaching time, like a pickle jar, is limited. What you fill it with, is up to you. The pickle jar represents school teaching time.

According to this theory, imagine you have a big empty pickle jar. Fill it with golf balls (teaching activity such as a lesson) until it can't take no more. The golf balls leave gaps. Drop in some marbles (important school activity such as games, staff meetings, seminars, music drama events etc.), give the jar a shake, and let the marbles drop into those gaps. Next, take some sand (cleaning, farm activities, guidance and counseling, talks etc.). Pour it into the even smaller spaces that are left, until the jar appears to be completely full. Finally, finish it off with water. Pour in water (meaningless chat, time on net) until the jar can't take anything else, and then screw the lid on! Wright (2002).

The theory requires that teachers prioritize school activities according to the limited school time available. They should give priority to teaching time (class lessons), this should be followed by important school activities such as games, meetings, seminars and others of same type. Which can be done outside teaching hours of school. Other less important activities such as cleaning, farm activities, talks etc. can still be fitted in the school program without affecting lessons. Same to meaningless chats and hours spent on net.

If one schedules important school activities such as games, meetings and seminars during teaching time, it becomes difficult to fit teaching lessons. Same to other less important activities such as cleaning, farm activities and talks etc., As a result, class lessons suffer as they go unattended or reduced.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

This chapter focused on review of literature on how teachers manage their instructional time in secondary schools in Kenya and in particular in EMC. The review of the literature was derived from books, thesis, journals, newspapers, internet and other documents. These were the opinions, knowledge, and attributes of various studies and people towards such a study, Sulo (2012).

The following are topics under which literature were reviewed;

- (i) Teacher preparation in teaching;
- (ii) Teaching time interruptions;
- (iii) Teacher commitment to instruction;
- (iv) Teacher absenteeism.

For quality teaching and learning to take place, teacher presence, teacher preparedness and good lesson delivery are most important. This study was aimed at analyzing how teachers use time to prepare and deliver lessons to learners with respect to student academic achievement.

2.2 Teacher Preparation in Teaching

Lee (2004) asserts that, organization and planning are critical to engaging students and maximizing student achievement. Student achievement is closely hinged to teacher organizational abilities and delivery of lessons. According to Ngware (2015) study done by African Population and Health and Research Centre (APHRC) in both private and public secondary schools in major towns in Kenya. The study revealed that between 35 percent to 40 percent of lesson time is lost during teaching. For instance, the teacher is busy marking assignments, looking for teaching guides and other materials, closing doors and arranging seating positions among other things that do not contribute directly to learning. According to this study, this is a poor manifestation of poor lesson planning or lack of it. The huge loss in teaching time in class presents a more serious issue than teacher absenteeism. This is how lesson preparation contributes to the success of teaching and effective time management.

Teacher lesson preparation involves planning and making schemes of work, lesson plans and record of work previously covered. It also includes content preparation, selection of teaching aids and reference materials. It is important to note that this planning and organization of lessons using professional documents are time

bound. It was thus important to analyze the role of time management aspect to teaching and learning achievement.

Mwaka et al (2014) asserts that good planning is the first step to an effective class and one of the main tasks of an excellent teacher. According to them, careful and thoughtful planning considers the following important factors; maximizing instructional time, address standards, activate prior knowledge and confront misconceptions. In addition, address diverse characteristics and learning needs of the learners as well as keep useful records. This implies that good planning of lessons ensures proper management of teaching time reduces class management issues and focuses more on instruction, thus increasing learner achievement.

According to Aiyepetu (2006) there is need to emphasize measures that teachers should adopt in teaching and learning of mathematics; proper preparation before each lesson, effective use of teaching aids, giving of regular exercises during lesson, assisting each student during lessons to correct errors encountered while solving problems. Mastery of subject content and taking time to understanding learner needs are crucial components of teacher preparation that results in good performance. However, these are only achieved through good lesson preparation by teachers. Contrary, a poorly prepared teacher is likely to display poor mastery of subject content, disorderly in lesson presentation and teach without teaching aids where required. Critical observation, shows that this scenario emanate from poor management of teaching time in preparation of lessons among teachers that result in little student achievement.

2.3 Teaching Time Interruptions

It's common to find teachers and learners engaging in activities during teaching time which were not planned in the course of the school teaching program. For instance, staff meetings, departmental meetings, games, symposia, local leaders address, guidance and counseling fora, farm activities and cleanliness. In many occasions, these hours are never recovered and go a long way in impacting negatively on syllabus coverage and ultimately learner achievement.

Leonard (2003) reports that a study conducted in eight Louisiana (USA) school districts supports his earlier findings in Canadian schools. According to him, these strongly suggests that continuing misuse of scheduled class time through regular encroachments from outside the parameters of the classroom serve to erode instructional time and minimize learning opportunities. To him, many teachers remain frustrated and indignant about their inability to better control the learning environment. School managers, who are also teachers, are in charge of teaching and learning programs of a school and therefore they dictate what goes in a school set up.

These leaves teachers with no control of teaching time. They can interrupt teaching program for guidance and counseling forum, local leaders address and farm activities among others. This study was therefore, concerned with how teachers manage teaching time in class, to enable completion syllabus on time and ultimately better student learning achievement. This assertion supports the purpose of conducting this study. This is because, however the learners could be good, relevant applied teaching methodology and availability of learning resources, without proper use of the planned teaching time, the objectives of teachers during lessons will be curtailed significantly.

In USA, instructional time is further explored through the time lost to student discipline issues in the classroom and time lost to non-instructional issues, such as interruptions from outside the class, fundraising events and other school-wide activities, NEA research, (2006). Though according to this report, time on instruction is higher for USA schools. Data available on instructional time does not account for absenteeism of students and teachers, and does not exclude class time spent on student discipline, non-instructional activities and external interruptions. This report claims that, the more discipline problems there are in schools and classrooms, the greater the loss of instructional time. Hence, reduced opportunities for student learning, that results in less student achievement.

Teaching time management has been a challenge to many African nations. For instance, in Kenya, students recently lost six weeks of instructional time in two years alone because of teachers' strikes, Kibiwott & Ngare (2008). Teacher and student strikes is another big form of teaching interruption in secondary schools, mostly experienced in developing countries. This problem impedes teaching and learning. In developed and developing countries, learners' lose teaching time. However, the magnitude and reasons vary significantly depending on the social factors. For instance, reasons for instructional time loss by teachers and learners in developed nations are discipline related, while for developing nations are resource related in nature.

2.4 Teacher Commitment to Instruction

Teacher commitment refers to the ability of teachers to dedicate their energy and time to the teaching process. These include being in school as required, preparing lessons and participating in all school activities. These ensure proper management of teaching time that ultimately benefit the learners. It also involve being innovative and initiative in teaching, as well as going extra mile to assist learners.

Kwok-kwai (2006) argued that teachers who are dedicated and committed to teaching might facilitate school-based innovations or reforms that are meant to benefit students' learning and development. In fact, teacher commitment and engagement has

been identified as one of the most critical factors in the success of education (Huberman, 1997, Nais, 2002).

Teachers' ability to deliver quality lessons in teaching determines coverage of syllabus and student achievement. It also determines confidence learners have on teachers. According to SMASSE survey in Malawi, done by UNICEF (2010), it reported the following categories of teachers; first, teachers who have good content mastery. The following is portrayed in their teaching; take time to plan, think about the delivery process with their students in mind, are sequential in their teaching and most often student centered. Secondly, teachers who 'lack' the time and their teaching portray that they; do not take time to plan, do not think about the delivery process, are not sequential in their teaching, are out of touch with the syllabus, are not student centered and in many cases confuse students. The third category, are those who lack content mastery. They; cannot explain concepts satisfactorily, often misleading students unknowingly. This implies that some teachers in secondary schools are neither committed to their work nor to their clients who are the learners. This poses a lot of challenges on quality of teaching and learning in schools. The evidence of minimal commitment among teachers is shown by improper time management that often results in incompleteness of syllabus in the required time.

According to UNICEF Malawi, (2010) report, some teachers in government schools, allegedly neglect their duties. Which leads to non-completion of syllabus as scheduled. This made students to get excited as annual examinations scheduled approached. Parents exerted pressure on teachers to complete the syllabus on time.

2.4.1 Teacher Absenteeism

One of the major indicators of teacher's lack of commitment to teaching is the issue of teacher absenteeism. This is a persistent problem in many countries as it tends to reduce the quality of education and results in poor performance of learners, Lucas et al (2012). Teacher absence sends teaching activities to a complete halt. No learning can take place in the event a teacher is absent. Unless it is well managed, by for instance having a substitute teacher. Otherwise, it remains the biggest form of school teaching time wastage loophole. This is the worst form of teacher poor commitment to teaching process a teacher can display. This is because teacher absenteeism is unethical practice among teachers.

According to Ngware (2015) a study conducted by African Population and Health and Research Centre (APHRC) revealed that teachers absentee are up to 17 percent in public schools. Teachers are absent due to three main reasons; illness, attending to school official business and personal issues. It is important that

arrangements are done to recover the lost time. There are two ways; one is to ask a teacher to step in and later the absent teacher to take over that time. The other method is in cases where a teacher plans to be away, for example attending official activities, the teacher can teach prior to that time.

In Kenya, it has been a norm that teachers don't complete syllabus with students in the required time. Usually, teachers ask for extra time yet curriculum has been organized to take certain stipulated time, Drucker (2005). The extra time requested usually comes during school holidays, weekends, morning or evenings. This indicates that secondary school instructional programs have time utilization challenges that causes syllabus not to be completed in the required time.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This chapter described the overall research design and rationale which was employed in this study. It also included discussion of the study area, target population, sampling procedures and sample size, data collection, piloting, data analysis, validity and reliability, ethical considerations and lastly the summary of the chapter.

3.2 Study Area

The study was conducted in EMC with four administrative Sub-counties namely; Keiyo South, Keiyo North, Marakwet East and Marakwet West. There were 105 registered public secondary schools in this county as at 2014.

3.3 Research Design

The study was both quantitative and qualitative in research approach. The researcher adopted descriptive survey design for this study. This is because it involved quantifiable data collected using questionnaire and statement descriptions collected using interview schedule as well. Survey design was most appropriate for this study because it covered a large area and involved a big population of respondents.

3.4 Target Population

The study targeted public secondary schools in EMC that had presented candidates for KCSE examinations for 5 years giving a clear trend of performance. They were 75 secondary schools that had offered KCSE examinations by 2013. The target population for DOS officers was 75 while that of teachers was 385.

3.5 Sampling Procedures and Sample Size

A sample is a finite part of statistical population where properties are studied to gain information about the whole, Sulo (2012). According to Mugenda and Mugenda (2003), 30 % of the population will be a representative number. The researcher used stratified random sampling method to select schools for the study. Schools were put into four strata according to school status National, Extra-county, County and Sub-county. Total schools in the county for the study were 75. The county comprised of Keiyo South sub-county with 23 schools, Keiyo North 16, Marakwet East 13 and Marakwet West 13. In each sub-county, schools were put into strata as follows;

Keiyo South 23; Sub-county schools 13, county 7, extra county 3 and national 0
Keiyo North 16; Sub-county schools 7, county 4, extra county 3 and national 1
Marakwet East 13; Sub-county schools 7, county 4, extra county 2 and national 0
Marakwet West 23; Sub-County schools 12, county 7, extra county 3 and national 1.

From each strata, schools were randomly selected to provide samples for the study as follows; Keiyo South; Sub-county category 4 schools were sampled, county 2, extra county 1 and national 0, giving a total of 7 schools for the sample. Keiyo North; Sub county category 2 schools were sampled, county 1, extra county 1 and national 1, giving a total of 5 schools for the sample. Marakwet East; Sub-county category 2 schools were sampled, county 1, extra county 1 and national 0, giving a total of 4 schools for the sample. Marakwet West; Sub-county category 3 schools were sampled, county 2, extra county 1 and national 1, giving a total of 7 schools for the sample. The table below shows the summary of the sample size.

Table 3.1: Sample Size

Name of Sub-County	Strata (School Category) and Sample Size									
	Sub-County	Sample	County	Sample	Extra-County	Sample	National	Sample	Total Schools	Total Sample Size
Keiyo South	13	4	7	2	3	1	0	0	23	7
Keiyo North	7	2	4	1	4	1	1	1	16	5
Marakwet East	7	2	4	1	2	1	0	0	13	4
Marakwet West	12	3	7	2	3	1	1	1	23	7
Total									75	23

Source: County Director of Education Office, Elgeyo Marakwet County, (2015)

In each school sampled purposive sampling method was used to select 23 DOS officers to participate in the study. According to Alexander (2004) purposive sampling is used in qualitative research to focus on the perspectives of those who are known to experience the phenomenon of interest. The DOS officers are in charge of academic teaching and learning programs such as timetabling, teaching lessons, remedial lessons and examinations. Therefore, this group provided vital information required for this study.

Stratified purposive sampling was also used to select subjects for the study. The subjects were put into strata according to departments as follows; Languages, Mathematics & Sciences, Humanities and Technical & Applied arts. In each stratum, purposive sampling was used to select subjects which were considered wide by teachers as follows; English was sampled for languages, biology and physics were sampled for mathematics and sciences category, geography was considered for humanities while agriculture was picked for technical and applied arts.

Respondent teachers were selected from teachers who teach English, biology, physics, geography and agriculture; subjects known to have wide syllabus in the 8.4.4 system secondary school cycle. Simple random sampling was used to select 1 teacher, teaching each of these 5 subjects in the respective department. These translate to 5 teacher respondents per school sampled. Purposive sampling was used to select a teacher for a particular subject if a school has one teacher for that subject. Therefore, the

total number of subject teachers who took part in the study was 115. This brings the total number of respondents to 138 for this study including the DOS officers.

3.6 Data Collection Instruments

The researcher used questionnaires, in-depth individual interviews and document analysis as data collection instruments.

3.6.1 Questionnaire

This instrument was appropriate for this study because data was collected from a large number of respondents within a very short time. There was one type of questionnaire that was filled by teachers teaching; Physics, English, Agriculture Biology and Geography which were identified by teachers to have wide syllabus during piloting stage.

3.6.2 Interview Schedules

The researcher applied in-depth interview method to collect qualitative data. The data collected was analyzed according to themes and concepts. The interview conversations were conducted person to person with the Director of Studies. The interview of collecting data was continued until no new information emerged from the discussion on a point.

3.6.3 Document Analysis

The researcher requested the DOS copies of teaching time table, routine time table, and remedial teaching time table and teacher lesson attendance records. In addition, academic performance records of both Form one end of year results (2014) as well as previous five years Form four KCSE results were also requested for. Each document provided specific information sought.

3.7 Piloting of Research Instruments

The piloting process was done prior to the actual research data collection exercise. This was conducted in Moiben Zone, in the neighbouring county of Uasin Gishu. This was meant to familiarize with the procedure and streamline the study. Most importantly, to test the validity and reliability of the research instruments.

3.7.1 Validity

The researcher used expert review to validate the research instruments for this study. The researcher sought assistance of experts in the CIEM department and particularly the two study supervisors helped in checking validity of the instruments.

3.7.2 Reliability

Reliability was done using test-retest technique. Questionnaires were administered to the same respondents after 2 weeks. The instruments yielded a reliability co-efficient (r) =0.89 (the Pearson's product moment co-efficient), after the two sets of data were collected and analyzed. In this study, reliability for qualitative data was ensured by continuing with data collection through interview, until there was no new data emerging. Interpretations of different explanations of concepts was done, which yielded same points for different interviewees.

3.8 Data Collection Procedures

Researcher sought permission from NACOSTI, the County Director of Education (CDE) and the County Commissioner of the study area. The process of data collection was done in the schools sampled, by researcher himself. The researcher gave questionnaires to the randomly selected five teachers for the five subjects and then conducted interview with the DOS. The requested for documents for analysis was done.

3.9 Data Analysis

The approach for this study was descriptive statistical method. Quantitative data from questionnaires was analyzed using statistical methods with the help of SPSS software. Data in form of frequencies and percentages were output on tables.

Qualitative data obtained from interview schedules was analyzed using descriptive method.

The analysis of documents was done by referencing on them to confirm data authenticity in questionnaires and arguments by interviews.

3.9.1 Ethical Considerations

The researcher discussed and sought consent from the respondent teachers to take part in the study as subjects. He also assured the respondents that their identity, schools, documents, reports they provide and any other information will be kept anonymous. The researcher acknowledged the work of other scholars where applicable and avoided plagiarism.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA ANALYSIS, PRESENTATION, INTERPRETATION AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Introduction

The topics of discussion were guided by the research objectives and research questions of the study. The analyzed data were presented in tables using frequencies and percentages. The study presentation analysis was hinged on the following themes of this research; teacher preparation on teaching, teaching time interruptions and teacher commitment. The response rate was 100% this provided good data for analysis. The data was analyzed and interpreted according to objectives of the study and addressing the purpose of the study.

4.2 Teacher Preparation Towards Time Management Strategies in Public Secondary Schools

Results on teacher preparation towards time management strategies in public secondary schools show the following; on presenting lesson content to learners, 42.6% of teachers occasionally face challenges, while 10.4% often encounter them and another 2.6% always experience. About half of teachers face challenges during their teaching in delivering content to learners. This implies teachers do not prepare adequately for teaching and consequently lose on teaching time which results in non-completion of syllabus for a class on time scheduled.

4.2.1 Preparation for Teaching as a Strategy in Management of Teaching Time

Table 4.1. Show teachers own rating on the use of schemes of work revealed that, slightly more than half, 55.7%, rated themselves as good users and another 22.6% as very good. Another 18.3% rated themselves satisfactory, 1.7% fair and another 1.7% poor users of this professional document. Teacher use of it is generally good. According to Sahu (2014) a well prepared scheme of work plan is a useful aid for teachers for maneuvering teaching in the right direction and completing the task in time.

Table 4.1: Teacher Preparation and Use of Schemes of Work as a Strategy of Time Management

Teachers' Response	Teachers' Use of Schemes of Work Rating		Teachers' Lesson Plan Use Rating	
	Frequency	Percent (%)	Frequency	Percent (%)
Poor	2	1.7	N/A	N/A
Fair	2	1.7	2	1.7
Satisfactory	21	18.3	16	13.9
Good	64	55.7	34	29.6
Very Good	26	22.6	14	12.1
N/A	N/A	N/A	49	42.6
Total	115	100.0	115	100.0

Source: Field data, 2015.

According to the table 4.1, 29.6% of teacher respondents rated themselves as good users of lesson plans, 12.1% very good, 13.9% satisfactory and only 1.7% fair. In practice, teachers do not prepare lessons and therefore don't use them. Instead, they use lesson notes which have lesson objectives, teaching methods, teaching activities and resources as well as references. This saves them planning time. Experienced teachers have advantage over incoming teachers. This is because they have internalized teaching procedures, though still, good teaching requires good preparation. According to Duncan & Met (2010), a well prepared lesson plan gives the teacher a sense of direction when he enters the classroom. It also helps the teacher to know when to start and where to stop. It helps in managing teaching time indicated on each sections of the lesson plan.

4.2.2 Content Presentation Strategies in Teaching Time Management

Teachers can experience challenges when presenting lesson content to learners in class if they are not well prepared. According to the table 4.2, teachers revealed that 44.4% rarely have problems, 42.6% occasionally face them, while 10.4% often encounter them and another 2.6% always experience. From these figures, it is evident that about half of teachers face challenges during their teaching in delivering content to learners.

The reason for this scenario is not that teachers don't know concepts but they have not prepared adequately for lessons. The consequence of teaching ill prepared is that the teacher is likely to face content presentation challenges in class. The results of these are; the teacher is not consistent with facts (misleading learners) hence takes more time clarifying them, teacher spends more time on student questions and teacher loses student confidence.

This is in agreement with Duncan & Met (2010) that when teachers go to class to teach without a lesson plan or a work plan the results will actually be; poor or reduced learning which actually results in confusion of the learners by the teacher, frustration for both the teacher and the students and waste of time and effort for all. Though, DOS reported that it's only a small number who normally face challenges. The DOS attributed this to poor lesson preparation before teaching which also the respondents alluded to.

Table 4.2: Content Presentation in Teaching Time Management

Teachers' Response	Teachers' Challenge on Content Presentation	
	Frequency	Percent (%)
Rarely	51	44.4
Occasionally	49	42.6
Often	12	10.4
Always	3	2.6
Total	115	100.0

Source: Field data, 2015.

4.3 Teaching Interruptions and Time Management in Public Secondary Schools

4.3.1 Teaching Time Interruptions

The occurrence of teaching time interruptions in schools is one of the things that retard teaching and learning in many schools. According to the table 4.3, 56.5% of teachers revealed that this happens occasionally, 11.3% indicated that they experienced often and 32.2% rarely experience this occurrence. Actually in total, about 67.8% of teachers face this problem in their schools. Such unplanned teaching activities that form teaching interruptions are on a high side. This reveals the extent of the problem and how it impacts negatively on teaching and learning time. These forms the evidence of improper management of teaching time in schools and one of the factors that are responsible for teachers' incompleteness of syllabus on time.

Table 4.3: Teaching Interruptions Experienced by Teachers

Teachers' Response	Frequency	Percent (%)
Rarely	37	32.2
Occasionally	65	56.5
Often	13	11.3
Total	115	100.0

Source: Field data, 2015.

Leonard (2003) asserts that the continued misuse of scheduled class time through regular encroachments from outside the parameters of the classroom, serve to erode instructional time and minimize learning opportunities.

There are other interruptions which may not be organized by schools, for example in Kenya, students recently lost six weeks of instructional time in two years alone because of teachers' strikes, Kibiwott & Ngare (2008). This is a big loss of teaching time students are subjected to, on issues which can be resolved.

Contrary, DOS officers claimed that interruptions of teaching time are not a common phenomenon. According to them, it's only on unavoidable circumstances (emergencies) that this can be allowed to happen. This means that teachers plan lessons with these 'lesson interruptions' in mind, which in this case cannot qualify to be lesson interruptions. School activities that can be planned are; half-term breaks, academic days, AGMs, sports and games, tours and field excursions, symposiums, G/C sessions and so on. While occurrence which cannot be planned include; teacher's sickness (in cases where one teacher teaches a subject alone), teachers' and students' strikes, staff funerals, school fees breaks (where half-term breaks are not available), impromptu visits by prominent persons among other emergencies.

As to whether these teaching time interruptions are educational or not, the teacher respondents were divided. In the table 4.4 it shows that 67.8% of the respondents indicated that they are educational activities and thus necessary. While 32.2% indicated they are not educational and therefore not necessary. To this group it is a time wasting exercise. This is similar to what NEA research (2006) found out in their study on school instructional time. That a lot of time is lost to student discipline issues in the classroom and time lost to non-instructional issues, such as interruptions from outside the class, fundraising events and other school-wide activities. This is supported by studies done by Gilman and Knoll (2004). Who determined that as much as 60% of

the typical secondary school day was consumed by non- instructional events such as class changes, lunch periods and extra-curricular activities.

Table 4.4: Nature of Teaching Interruptions and Time Management Strategies

Teachers' Response	Nature of Teaching Interruptions		Compensation for Interrupted Lesson	
	Frequency	Percent (%)	Frequency	Percent (%)
Yes	78	67.8	96	83.5
No	37	32.2	19	16.5
Total	115	100.0	115	100.0

Source: Field data, 2015.

Similarly, DOS responses varied on this matter. Some of them said they are educational activities, while others were categorical that they are not educational. They explained that such interruptions are programs that aid learning, but teachers prioritized them against teaching of lessons. Consequently, these interruptions are educational activities in nature. As a result they become emergencies. However, the solution to this problem is to strike a balance by having these activities away from teaching time. Alternatively, they should be planned in schemes of work so that it doesn't interrupt the teaching process. By doing so, it will enable teaching time to be well managed and this will facilitate coverage of syllabus for a class on time.

Compensation for interrupted lesson is basically compensation of lost time caused by the interruption. Teachers were asked whether they compensate lost lessons or not. Compensation allows the teaching time lost to be recovered and coverage of work remains on course as planned. Therefore, it is one strategy of good management of teaching time.

The table 4.4 shows that a massive 83.5% of teachers indicated that they compensate while 16.5% gave the negative response. According to many DOS interviewed, most teachers compensate interrupted teaching time and they do this during prep time or on weekends. Drucker (2005) confirms these also, that teachers teach in the morning, evening and weekends to recover lost teaching time. Some teachers don't compensate at all, while a few said they at times compensate. The problem arises when the loss of lessons is caused by the school, teachers will not be willing to compensate as they consider it official.

Compensation of interrupted lesson helps manage teaching time. This is because teachers cannot be in school all through. There are cases such as sickness of the teacher or strikes which cannot be avoided by teachers.

Teachers are officers in charge of teaching and learning in schools. However, when issues of teaching interruptions come up, then it begs the question as to whether they are actually in charge. Teachers were asked this question and according to table 4.5 they had divided responses, 44.4% of them indicated that teachers have control of teaching time and 55.6% declined. When teachers are in control of their instructional time, then they are able to effectively manage their time to see that planned activities are accomplished.

The DOS officers were equally divided, according to some, “teachers have control of their teaching time and not influenced by other external factors. “To this group, consultations are done as to whether to allow interruptions or not”. While some said; “school management take control of teaching time of learners and don’t consult them”. It’s important to note also that school management are also teachers given responsibility of managing school teaching and learning activities. Therefore, the policy and decision they adopt on teaching interruptions, definitely impacts teaching process either positively or negatively. This is one of the decisions that make the difference between schools, in terms of quality of teaching provision and performance. Most likely, a school that has control of their teaching time organizes their activities well in such a way that its core purpose of teaching and learning is not compromised. Early planning and scheduling of urgent activities appropriately are crucial in a school set up to ensure its main function is not adversely affected.

Table 4.5: Teachers’ Authority over Teaching Interruptions and Effect on Syllabus Coverage

Teachers’ Response	Teachers’ Control of Teaching Time		Teaching Interruptions and Syllabus Coverage	
	Frequency	Percent (%)	Frequency	Percent (%)
Yes	51	44.4	99	86.1
No	64	55.6	16	13.9
Total	115	100.0	65	100.0

Source: Field data, 2015.

4.3.2 Effect of Teaching Interruption on Syllabus Coverage

It was also important to confirm whether the occurrences of teaching interruptions in a school, slow down syllabus coverage. This effect, ultimately make teachers to do extra teaching time in order to complete syllabus in the required time of school term. According to the table 4.5, 86.1% of teacher respondents concurred while only 13.9% differed. This means that teaching time is commonly interrupted for other non-teaching activities and these results in incompleteness of syllabus on time. Assertion by (Abadzi, 2007, Gillies and Quijada, 2008) supports this claim that in most of African countries, students are often taught for only a fraction of the intended number of hours. Normally, instructional time is wasted through informal school closures, teacher absenteeism, delays, early departures and poor use of classroom time.

The solution of this problem is to plan the teaching activities well in advance and if unavoidable interruption in teaching happens, then most likely they are a few, whose lost lessons can be recovered easily without affecting the school routine. Otherwise, if this is not done, then compensation of missed lessons becomes difficult and lessons are lost. It's this losing of lessons without compensation that in the long run necessitates extra time teaching in order to catch up and complete syllabus in time. Time is a scarce resource and compensation at times become difficult because other activities are also scheduled. It is such scenarios that built up to late completion of syllabus which yields dismal student achievement.

4.4 Teacher's Commitment on Instruction as a Strategy for Management of Teaching Time

Commitment to teaching process by teachers determines the level of preparation for lessons, lesson attendance, learner motivation and general creativity as well as teacher initiative. Basically, a committed teacher is proactive, results oriented and work with minimum supervision.

Lesson attendance is a key parameter of measuring management of teaching time. Actual teaching takes place when a teacher interacts with learners in a lesson. The more the teachers attend their lessons the better the management of teaching time and learning achievement. The converse is also true.

Teachers were asked as to whether they attend all their lessons where possible as a measure of their commitment to teaching time. The table 4.6 shows their responses. Teacher proportion of 80.0% of them indicated that they attend all lessons where possible. This demonstrates their commitment to teaching time. While 20.0% indicated that they don't attend all. Meaning, out of 10 daily lessons, a class misses 2 lessons daily, accumulating to 10 lessons missed in one week alone. In Kenya, according to

Ongeri & Bii (2012), teacher absenteeism has been cited as one of the main factors that is responsible for poor student performance in secondary schools.

According to DOS, teachers rarely miss their lessons. If they miss for some reason, they compensate during informal hours of school. In some schools where there are a number of teachers for a subject, if a teacher is absent, others step in. This arrangement referred to as ‘team teaching’ enables the lessons running and hence good utilization of teaching time. Missing of lessons without any apparent reason by a teacher, depict a person who is unmotivated and non-professional. This problem is also evident in developed nations. For instance, in USA, teacher absenteeism averages between 8-10% (Staffing Industry Report, 2009; Ramirez, 1999; Warren, 2000). This equals to over one full year of every child’s elementary education being taught by a substitute teacher. Daily, few teacher lesson absences accrue to become a lot of teaching time wastage of learner’s time. The immediate impact of this is the incomplete syllabus coverage and later low learner achievement.

Table 4.6: Teacher’s Commitment on Instruction as a Strategy of Teaching Time Management

Teachers’ Response	Teachers’ Lesson Attendance		Teachers’ Job Satisfaction		Teachers’ Timely Completion of Syllabus	
	Frequency	Percent (%)	Frequency	Percent (%)	Frequency	Percent (%)
Strongly Disagree	0	0	0	0	0	0
Disagree	0	0	9	7.8	0	0
Undecided	0	0	5	4.3	0	0
Agree	23	20.0	60	52.2	46	40.0
Strongly Agree	92	80.0	41	35.7	69	60.0
Total	115	100.0	115	100.0	115	100.0

Source: Field data 2015

Basically, someone who is not satisfied with the current job, possess tendencies of non-committal to his /her work. The level of commitment to work is determined by job satisfaction among other factors. From the field results, the DOS were unhappy lot with their job of teaching. All DOS interviewed responded that the relationship between teacher job satisfaction and teaching is quite strong. Nearly all of them said; ‘Given another chance, they will not take up same job of teaching unless their terms of service

are, adequately remunerated like their colleagues in other sectors'. Job satisfaction determines teacher's level of commitment to teaching. Gupta and Gehlawat (2013) confirms that job satisfaction has been found to be a significant determinant of teacher's organizational commitment and in turn, a contributor to school's effectiveness. Poor job satisfaction causes low level of commitment among teachers. This result in inadequate teaching preparation and poor lesson attendance that yield to loss of teaching time.

From these reactions, teachers felt that their welfare was not well taken care of as compared to their counterparts in other government departments. There is no doubt that this affects their teaching commitment negatively, which has far-reaching implication on management of teaching time. Consequently, learning achievement too.

According to table 4.6, 35.7% of respondent teachers indicated that they strongly agree that they are satisfied with their job of teaching, 52.2% indicated that they agree, 4.3% undecided and 7.8% disagreed. In general, a total of 87.9% (35.7% plus 52.2%) of teachers are satisfied with their teaching jobs and only 12.1% (4.3% plus 7.8%) are not. Motivated teachers in terms of job satisfaction are committed to teaching. This enables them manage teaching time effectively completing instructional tasks on time, eventually resulting in better performance.

One method of rating teachers in terms of teaching time management is their ability to complete syllabus on time. However, not only completing syllabus on time but also with high standards that result in good performance.

The table 4.6 shows the responses of teachers where 60.0% strongly agreed and 40.0% agreed that teacher commitment to teaching determines the timely completion of syllabus. This means that teacher commitment to teaching is directly proportional to timely completion of syllabus for a class. This is in agreement with (Huberman, 1997, Nais, 2002) that teacher commitment and engagement has been identified as one of the most critical factors in the success of education. In this case success of education also includes completing syllabus on time which corresponds to ultimate good learner achievement.

Creativity and innovativeness in teaching is a skill teachers possess when they are committed and motivated. It involves teachers devising other ways of solving problems. These occur in cases where conventional methods are not appropriate, seeking better methods of teaching certain concepts or seeking for appropriate teaching aids. Teachers have to be creative and innovative in their teaching to device ways of managing teaching time to cover work planned. For example, assigning students some tasks to do outside a lesson, helps to reduce work that would have taken lesson time. Directly engaging students on practical work help save teaching time. Instead of

discussing a practical content and later letting students do practical. Similarly, where possible, the use of a projector to conduct a lesson saves a lot of teaching time.

Table 4.7: Teacher’s Creativity in Teaching as a Strategy of Time Management

Teachers’ Response	Teachers’ Creativity and Innovativeness		Teachers’ Doing Extra Work for Learners	
	Frequency	Percent (%)	Frequency	Percent (%)
Strongly Disagree	0	0	0	0
Disagree	2	1.7	2	1.7
Undecided	5	4.3	2	1.7
Agree	55	47.9	58	50.5
Strongly Agree	53	46.1	53	46.1
Total	115	100.0	115	100.0

Source: Field data 2015

The table 4.7 show that teachers numbering 46.1% indicated they strongly agree that they are creative and innovative in their teaching, 47.9% agree, 4.3% were undecided and only 1.7% disagreed. This implies 94.0% (46.1% plus 47.9% plus) of respondents are creative and innovative and therefore are committed to their work of teaching. The DOS interviewed gave similar opinions, “In fact some improvise on teaching aids”.

They also reported that teachers do what they can to ensure learners succeed in their learning. “Revision is done on time and learners are motivated and guided on their revision”. One reason that makes some teachers not to be creative and innovative in their teaching is the handling of large work load. This does not provide a teacher the time to engage in innovating new skills of solving problems or coming up with other teaching materials.

Teaching secondary school level involves doing a lot of extra work for learners to succeed. This include conducting remedial lessons, looking for teaching aids, taking students for excursions (field work), organizing subjects contests and marking learners assignments. Teachers who perform these extra activities to improve teaching and learning are therefore committed to teaching process.

These activities help in managing teaching time as well exposing students to varied learning opportunities which may not be available in class. For example, according to Mwaka et al (2014) class assignments help provide immediate feedback to the teacher on the learner’s ability. Good teaching cannot be possible without class

assignments given to learners. In addition, providing learners with individual difference such as the slow learners and gifted learners is an extra work for teachers.

The table 4.7 shows 46.1% of teachers strongly agree that they do extra work for learners, 50.5% agree, 1.7% were undecided and another 1.7% disagreed. In general 96.6% (46.1% plus 50.5%) indicate that were in agreement. This is a high degree of diligence teachers possess. According to many DOS interviewed they explained that, "Committed teachers will always enable their students post good results in examinations and achieve more". These extra work for teachers, provide more learning opportunities for learners. They fill gaps in the learning process, expose learners to real world as well as enabling learners to master and concretize learning concepts. Ultimately, it improves leaner achievement.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Introduction

This chapter is a presentation of conclusions and recommendations of the research findings and discussions from the previous chapter. They were organized according to the objectives of the study.

5.2 Summary of the Findings

The following is the summary of the research findings for this study.

5.2.1 Lesson preparation towards time management strategies in public secondary schools in Elgeyo Marakwet County

A proportion, 42.6% of teachers don't prepare lesson plans. For those, 57.4% that prepare lesson plans, 78.3% of them are good users. This implies, many teachers do not achieve their lesson objectives of completing work planned in time. Nearly half of teachers, 46.0% use teaching materials occasionally in teaching. Teaching without use of teaching aids is time consuming and difficult for learners to concretize the concepts. A good number of teachers, 55.6% face challenges when presenting content to students. A teacher is likely to have problems during content presentation if he or she is inadequately prepared for teaching.

5.2.2 Teaching time interruptions in public secondary schools in Elgeyo Marakwet County

Many teachers, 67.8% experience teaching time interruptions. These are evidence of improper management of teaching time. A good number of teachers, 67.8% believe that teaching time interruptions are educational activities in nature and thus necessary. While 32.2% indicated they are not and therefore not necessary. A good amount of time is spent on non-instructional activities.

5.2.3 Teacher commitment towards time management strategies for instruction in public secondary schools in Elgeyo Marakwet County

Teacher proportion of 80.0% of them indicated that they attend all lessons where possible. This demonstrates their commitment to teaching. The number of teachers 87.9% indicated they are satisfied with their job of teaching. Motivated teachers in terms of job satisfaction are committed to teaching. Teachers, 60.0% strongly agreed that they

complete syllabus on time, 40.0% of them agreed that teacher commitment to teaching determines the timely completion of syllabus. The total number of teachers, 96.6% does extra work for learners. This is a high degree of diligence teachers possess. Extra work for learners, fill gaps in the learning process and exposes learners to real world experience as well as enabling learners to master learnt concepts.

5.3 Conclusions

According to objectives of this study as stated in chapter one, the following can be concluded as per findings in chapter four. Most teachers do not prepare adequately for teaching and as a result, lose a lot of teaching time. A larger proportion of teachers teach without lessons plans and teaching materials. A good number of teachers are having challenges in presenting content to the learners. Teaching interruptions are common in public secondary schools. Teachers are never in control of their teaching schedule hence has negative implication on instructional time management. Many teachers complete syllabus on time by teaching during unstipulated teaching hours of school. Teachers are generally committed to their teaching duties and like their job.

5.4 Recommendations

1. The county education administration should embark on refreshing teachers on lesson preparation.
2. Teachers should have control of their teaching time.
3. Teachers should lay more emphasis on quality teaching and learning as opposed to early completion of syllabus.
4. Teachers should not teach to cover syllabus during unofficial hours of school.
5. There is need for QASO officers to increase inspections in schools and pay more emphasis on time management in teaching.
6. Schools to assign Heads of Departments and Heads of Subjects the duty of performing internal inspection on teachers.
7. The KICD should consider reviewing the curriculum of Geography and Agriculture syllabus considered to have wide syllabi.

References

1. Abadzi, H. (2007). *Absenteeism and Beyond: Instructional Time Loss and Consequences*, DC: World Bank Policy Research Working Paper, No. 4376 (October); <http://go.worldbank.org/YTOZYABWK0>

2. Aiyepeku, T. (2006). *Inspection of Schools and Colleges*. Ibadan: Gold Press.
3. Del Siegele, P. (2011) *Reliability in Quantitative & Qualitative Research*. Beverly Hills, CA. Sage.
4. Drucker, P (2005): *The Five Deadly Businesses Sins*. The Wall Street Journal, online edition,. December 27, 2005
5. Drucker, P (2007). *The Effective Executive* (Classic Drucker Collection) Paperback.
6. Duncan, G, & Met, M. (2010). *STARTALK: From paper to practice*. College Park, MD: National Foreign Language Center at the University of Maryland. Available at www.startalk.umd.edu/lesson_planning.
7. Gichunga, S (2011), *Factors influencing the provision of holiday tuition in Laikipia West District*; University of Nairobi, Kenya: Published Thesis.
8. Gillies, M and Quijada, S(2008) *Teacher Absenteeism in Schools*. Published Journal.
9. Gilman, D., & Knoll, S. (2004). *Increasing instructional time. What are the priorities and how do they affect the alternatives?* *NASSP Bulletin*, 68(470), 41–44.
10. Gupta, M & Gehlawat, M (2013) : *A Study of the Correlates of Organizational Commitment Among Secondary School Teachers*. Department of Education, M.D.U., Rohtak and C.R. College of Education, Rohtak, respectively (Issues and Ideas in Education Vol. 1 March 2013pp. 59–71)
11. Huberman, M. (1997) *The Lives of Teachers* J. Neufeld Trans. London: Cassell Villiers House.
12. Kenya Education Sector Support Programme 2005 - 2010: Ministry of Education Science and Technology; *delivering quality education and training to all Kenyans*. Government Printer, Nairobi.
13. Kibiwott, K. and Ngare, P. (2008, July 14). *Riots become more Violent and Frequent*. *Nairobi: Daily Nation*, p.5.
14. KNEC Report: KCSE 2008 Results Examinations, Nairobi, Kenya
15. KNEC Report: KCSE 2010 Results Examinations, Nairobi, Kenya
16. KNEC Report: KCSE 2011 Results Examinations, Nairobi, Kenya
17. Kwok-wai, C. (2006) Hong Kong Teachers' Centre Journal ,Vol. 5© Hong Kong Teachers' Centre. *In-service teachers' motives and commitment in teaching*, Hong Kong. http://eacea.ec.europa.eu/education/eurydice/documents/facts_and_figures/taught_time_EN.pdf
18. Lee, P (2004) Journal: *Teaching preparation and achievement*, Vol 6th.

19. Leonard, L (1999) *Towards maximizing instructional time: The nature and extent of externally-imposed classroom interruptions*. Journal of School Leadership,; 9 (5), 454–474.
20. Leonard, L (2003) Journal of Educational Enquiry, Vol. 4, No. 2, *Optimizing by minimizing Interruptions and the erosion of teaching time*; Louisiana Tech University Ruston, Louisiana, United States of America.
21. Lucas.O, Bii, P.K., Sulo, T., Keter, B., Yano, E.M., Koskey, P. (2012): School Principal's Leadership Style: A Factor Affecting Staff Absenteeism in Secondary Schools.
22. Merream,E., (2009) Classroom Instruction in Schools. London, UK
23. Ministry of Education, Science and Technology (2007): A Report of the Taskforce on Affordable Secondary Education. Nairobi: Government Printer.
24. Mugenda, O. & Mugenda, A. (2003) Research Methods: Quantitative and Qualitative Approaches. African Center for technology Studies, Nairobi, Kenya.
25. Mwaka, M., Nabwire,V.K., & Musamas, J.,(2014). Essentials of Instruction: A Handbook for School Teachers. Moi University Press, Eldoret, Kenya.
26. Mwangi, N (2011). Determinants of academic performance in Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education in public secondary schools in Kiambu West district, Kenya. A published thesis in Kenya.
27. National Associa(n.d.). Retrieved June 30, 2004, from <http://www.nais.org> National Association of Independent Schools, NAIS (2002). Performance Appraisal (Example).
28. National Center for Education Statistics (NCES), (1993) U.S.A. Department of Education, Office of Educational Research and Improvement 'The Education Provisions Act, as amended (20 U.S.C. 1221e-1).statistics and other data related to education in the United States and in other nations. ''—Section 406(b) National Education Association (NEA), U`SA: 2006. Classroom Management Report
29. Ngugi, K. (2013) Ban on holiday tuition should be gazette, The Star, Kenya, 26 June.
30. Ngware, M.(2015) Journal: Teacher Absenteeism: The hidden Facts; African Population and Health and Research Centre, APHRC, Nairobi, Kenya
31. Nyagundi, Z (2012) Sub-County Education Report, Keiyo: KCSE Performance in Keiyo Secondary Schools, 2012; Iten, Kenya.
32. Okoronkwo, N. (2005); Classroom Instruction; Port Harcourt: David Stones Publishers.

33. Olusanjo, M. O. Lesson preparation and presentation during teaching practice. A paper presented at 2010/2011 teaching practice seminar for students. Osun State College of Education, Ila-Orangun.
34. Onger, L., & Bii, P.K., (2012): School Staff Absenteeism in Secondary Schools Published Journal
35. Sahu, K. (2014) Preparation for Teaching in Schools: Beverly Hills, CA. Sage.
36. Ramirez, A. (1999) Teaching Standards in USA High Schools: Published Thesis, New York.
37. SMASSE INSET (2010): The Republic of Malawi; Strengthening of Mathematics and Science in Secondary Education (SMASSE) INSET Malawi Phase II (2008-2012); Basic Education Cooperation Scheme Technical Cooperation, JICA and the Ministry of Education, Science and Technology (MoEST) of Malawi.
38. Staffing Industry Report, (2009) Washington, U.S.A.
39. Sulo, J. K. (2012). Factors Influencing Students' choice of Public Day Secondary Schools In Accessing Education in Kenya: A case of Eldoret Municipality. A published Thesis in Kenya.
40. UNICEF Malawi Education Report (2010): School Performance Evaluation, Malawi, Lilongwe.
41. [Uwezo Kenya Report \(2011\) National Assessment Report; July 19 2011.](#)
42. Warren, L (2000) Teacher Commitment on Teaching; A case study of Boston City. Published Thesis, USA.
43. Wong and Wong (1998). Research on Educational Scheduling activities.
44. Wright, J (2002): Time Management; The Pickle Jar Theory: Published in [Project Management.](#)

APPENDIX I: QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEACHERS

This questionnaire is aimed at collecting information for the research study that seeks *to analyze time management strategies for instruction employed by teachers and more specifically examine how teachers utilize teaching time and its relationship with academic performance in public secondary schools in Elgeyo Marakwet County.*

Please fill this questionnaire as honest as possible. The information you provide will be used for academic purposes only and its content will be confidential.

Please put a Tick (✓) where appropriate.

SECTION (A): Demographic Information

1. How many years have you been teaching?

(a) 0-5 years (b) 6-10 years (c) 11-15 years (d) 16-20 years

(e) 21-and above years

2. Which subject do you teach from the following options?

(a) Biology (b) Physics (c) English (d) Geography (e) Agriculture

3. What is your professional qualifications as a teacher ?

(a) Diploma Trained (b) Degree Untrained (c) Degree Trained

(d) Masters Trained (e) PhD Trained

4. Which category of school status does your school belong?

(a) National (b) Extra County (c) County (d) Sub-County

5. How do you rate your school in terms of academic performance?

(a) High performer (b) Performer (c) Average (d) Below average (e) Poor

SECTION (B): Teacher Preparation for Lessons

1. Do you prepare schemes of work?

Yes No

If No, give reason(s)

.....
.....
.....

2. How do you rate your use of schemes of work in your subject area in teaching?

Very Good Good Satisfactory Fair Poor

3. Do you normally prepare lesson plans before going to class?
Yes No

If Yes, give reason(s)

.....
.....
.....

If you prepare lesson plans, how do you rate your use of them in your subject area in teaching?

Very Good Good Satisfactory Fair Poor

4. How often do you use teaching aids / materials in your teaching?
Always Often Occasionally Rarely

5. How often do you encounter challenges in presenting subject content in your subject area?
Always Often Occasionally Rarely

6. Do you take time to think and select a suitable method of teaching in your subject area?
Yes No

7. Do you reflect on your lesson before going to present to learners?
Yes No

If Yes, give reason(s)

.....
.....
.....

8. Do you think proper preparation of teachers for teaching is key to good time management and timely completion of syllabus?
Yes No

Explain your choice

.....
.....
.....

SECTION (C): Teaching Time Interruptions and Management

1. Does your school has a calendar of activities?

Yes No

2. Do you consider school activities while scheming for lessons?

Yes No

3. How often do you experience interruptions in your teaching?

Always Often Occasionally Rarely

4. Do you think teaching time interruptions are educational in nature?

Yes No

Explain your response

.....
.....
.....

5. Do you normally compensate for interrupted lesson time?

Yes No

If Yes, give reason(s)

.....
.....
.....

6. Do teachers have control of their teaching time?

Yes No

Explain your response

.....
.....
.....
.....

7. Do you think teaching time interruptions slow down syllabus coverage in schools?

Yes No

Explain your response

.....
.....
.....

SECTION(D): Time for completion of syllabus for a class and its implication on learning achievement

1. How often do you complete what you plan to teach in a lesson?

Always Often Occasionally Rarely

2. Do you complete syllabus of work planned on schemes of work for a class at the end of school year in your subject area?

Yes No

If No, what are the reason (s)

.....
.....
.....

3. Do you attend lessons during unofficial hours of school in order to complete the syllabi in the stipulated time?

Yes No

4. Do you believe syllabi for your teaching subject is wide?

Yes No

If Yes, explain

.....

5. Do you think the time of completion of syllabus for a class has a direct impact on learning achievement?

Yes No

If Yes , explain

.....

6. Do you think completion of syllabus in time motivates learners to perform better in class?

Yes No

Give reason (s)

.....

SECTION(E): Teacher’s Commitment on Instruction

Please respond to the following statements by ticking on the appropriate column using the following:

SA-Strongly Agree, A-Agree, D-Disagree, SD- Strongly Disagree, U-Undecided

Cause		Perception				
		SA	A	U	D	SD
1.	I attend all my lessons where possible.					
2.	I’m satisfied with my job of teaching.					
3.	I strive to teach and complete syllabus in time.					
4.	I’m creative and innovative in my teaching.					
5.	I normally go extra mile to ensure my students succeed in learning.					

SECTION(F): Teachers’ Attitude Towards Time Management on Instruction.

Please respond to the following statements by ticking on the appropriate column using the following:

SA-Strongly Agree, A-Agree, D-Disagree, SD- Strongly Disagree, U-Undecided

Cause		Perception				
		SA	A	U	D	SD
1.	Lesson (s) missed should always be compensated.					
2.	As a teacher I keep time in teaching process.					
3.	Learning outcome depends on time spend on teaching.					
4.	Completion of instructional tasks is dependent on time management strategies employed by teachers.					

5. What is your opinion on the following statement?

Good time management in teaching results in quality learning and good performance.

.....

.....

.....

Thank you very much and God bless you

APPENDIX II: INTERVIEW GUIDE WITH THE DIRECTOR OF STUDIES

1. How many years has the officer served in this position?

2. What are the professional qualification of the officer?

3. Which category of school status does your school belong?

National, Extra County, County, Sub-County.

4. How do you rate your school in terms of academic performance?

Higher performer, Performer, Average, Below Average or Poor

5. Do teachers make schemes of work and lesson plans and use them adequately?

6. Does school administration carry out internal inspection to ensure teachers make and use schemes of work and lesson plans in teaching?

7. Do you think teachers prepare well before teaching?

8. Do you normally avail calendar of school activities in time for teachers?
9. Are there interruptions during teaching time? If are there, how often?
10. What are the reasons for class interruptions if they exist?
11. Are teaching interruptions educational in nature?
12. Are interrupted lessons compensated? If so what time is it done?
13. In your own opinion do you think teachers have control of their teaching time?
14. Do teaching time interruptions slow down timely completion of syllabus?
15. Do you have a remedial program? If so what times are they conducted?
16. What time of the year are teachers expected to complete syllabus with learners for a class? Do they make? If not what are the reasons?
17. Do teachers teach during informal hours in order to complete syllabi on time?

If so what time are they conducted?
18. Do you think the following subjects are wide compared to the number of lessons allocated? Biology, Physics, English, Geography & Agriculture
19. How many exams in a term do your students sit for? How much teaching time do exams take in a term?
20. Do you think good performance is dependent on early completion of the syllabus?

Does it motivate learners?
21. How often do teachers miss their lessons? What actions are taken on missed lessons?
22. Are teachers satisfied with their teaching job?
23. Are teachers creative and innovative in their teaching and do extra work to ensure learners excel?
24. Are missed lessons always compensated?
25. Do teachers keep time during teaching process?
26. Do you think teachers are generally committed to their work?
27. Do you think learning outcome depends on time spend on teaching?
28. Is there a relationship between teacher commitment in teaching process and the results posted in a given subject?
29. In your own assessment how do you rate your school in terms of management of instructional time?

Creative Commons licensing terms

Author(s) will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Education Studies shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflicts of interest, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated into the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).